

1 **Ribosomal vulnerability in the circulating tumor cell.**

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7 Accurate understanding of energy utilization and cellular expenditure in human cancer is important for
8 effective limitation of growth. We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the
9 peripheral blood of humans with stage IV breast to identify genes with ribosomal function exploited by the
10 tumor during dissemination. We describe here activation of the ribosomal subunit *RPS6KA2* and tRNA
11 synthetase subunit gene *FARS2* in the CTC in human cancer.

12 Citations

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14 1. Ebright RY, Lee S, Wittner BS, et al. Deregulation of ribosomal protein expression and translation
15 promotes breast cancer metastasis. *Science*. 2020;367(6485):1468-1473. doi:10.1126/science.aay0939
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